

1. Proactive
 - a. Shows initiative, task-oriented, directing, forward-thinking
 - b. Leans forward, direct eye contact, gestures
2. Supportive
 - a. Gives positive feedback or reassurance, tells jokes
 - b. Nodding, smiling, positive reinforcement
3. Collaborative
 - a. Asks proceeding questions, furthers partner's ideas
 - b. Open posture, hand gestures
4. Reliant
 - a. Asks for help, requires support for the task
 - b. Difficulty forming sentences, hesitant body language, seeking validation or assurance.
5. Withdrawn
 - a. Not engaging, brief responses, silence
 - b. Avoiding eye contact, leaning back
6. Dissatisfied
 - a. Expresses frustration actively, dissatisfied tone of voice
 - b. Eye rolling, restlessness
7. Confrontational
 - a. Questions partner's views, aggressive tone
 - b. Aggressive pointing, quick and sharp gestures
8. Critical
 - a. Not supporting partner's ideas, highlights partner's mistakes
 - b. Head shaking, sarcastic tone

Anna von Zansen 10.6.2024, adapted from student's interpersonal circle, Pennings, H. J. M., Brekelmans, M., Sadler, P., Claessens, L. C. A., van der Want, A. C., & van Tartwijk, J. (2018). Interpersonal adaptation in teacher-student interaction. *Learning and Instruction*, 55, 41–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2017.09.005>